

Mentorship, Capacity Development and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Calabar Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5234915

Abstract

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of mentorship, capacity development on teachers' job effectiveness in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of the study, six research questions and six null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The literature was reviewed based on the sub-variables of the study. The research design adopted for the study was ex-post facto. The purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting all the public secondary schools in the study area; while the simple random sampling technique was adopted to select a sample of 500 teachers as respondents for the study. The instrument used for the study was mentorship, capacity development and teachers' job effectiveness questionnaire. The hypotheses formulated were tested using independent t-test analysis statistics was used. The result of the analysis revealed among others that; instructional supervision and guidance services significantly influence teachers' job effectiveness in the study area. Based on the findings, conclusions and recommendations were made.

Keywords: Capacity development, guidance, job effectiveness, mentorship, teacher

Cite as: Etim, C. E., & Omorobi, G. O. (2020). Mentorship, capacity development and teachers' job effectiveness in Calabar Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning & Research*, 12(1&2), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5234915>

Introduction

Education is an instrument of social, mental and economic development, through which the right values and attitudes for proper development are inculcated. However, educational goals and objectives cannot be attained without competent teachers to implement formulated policies. As implementers of educational programmes, teachers require more than motivation and encouragement to do their job effectively. However, it is so unfortunate to see that teachers do not seem to have the required mentorship and capacity development programmes they should. This total negligence of teacher development particularly in the study area may be responsible for the teachers' job ineffectiveness and students' poor academic performance. There is a growing concern among parents, government, students and other stakeholders in the education

circle about what should be responsible for the dwindling performance of students in post-primary schools.

The position of the teacher in the process of education is substantial. Dembele (2005) shared the premise that unless teachers provide effective instruction and create a classroom environment conducive to learning, students will not achieve at high levels, even when essential material inputs are available and the curriculum is relevant. He argued that a good knowledge of demonstrably effective instructional practices is necessary but not sufficient condition for improving instructional practices without teachers who are able and ready to adopt such practices. Successful quality improvement in education will remain an impossible dream until the teacher can transfer knowledge most effectively. To International Institute for Educational Programme (IIEP, 2004), education for sustainable development growth can be threatened by low levels of education and training. The need for capacity building of the teacher is to equip him with the necessary skills to impart knowledge and have confidence in his profession to have global competitiveness is very crucial. Evidence for industrialized countries suggests that students of teachers with no professional preparation for teaching learn less than students who have fully prepared teachers (Darling-Hammond & Pest 2000). This work critically addressed teachers' supervision and guidance services and their job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar Education zone, Cross River State.

In view of this, Udowong (2014) conducted a study on supervision of teaching aids and teachers' role effectiveness in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Ten (10) public secondary schools were sampled out and used for the study. The study used five hundred (500) teachers who are currently in active service. Data obtained from respondents was possible through the use of a questionnaire designed, validated and tested for reliability before it was administered to respondents in the study area. Results obtained from the reliability test showed the reliability estimate of 0.86 to 0.92 respectively, which showed a high-reliability level of instrument consistency to measure it, is meant to measure. To test the hypothesis of the study, the simple percentage (%) descriptive analysis and mean (\bar{x}) difference was adopted to present the result. Results showed that (N=264(52.8%), \bar{X} =18.924, SD=2.862) respondents agreed that, supervision of teaching aids promote teachers' role effectiveness in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State; while (N=236 (47.2%), \bar{X} =14.676, SD=1.986) respondents perceived otherwise. From the foregone, it shows that supervision of teaching aids is essential in promoting teachers' role effectiveness in the study area. Based on the results obtained from the findings, it was recommended that adequate supervisory strategies should be put in place to promote effective monitoring and supervision of teachers' role effectiveness in the study area.

Instructional materials are useful for instructing and imparting relevant knowledge or learning experience to the students/pupils. The important thing to note about instructional material is that it has to be relevant to the teaching and learning experiences, and should be simple enough to manipulate by the students/pupils themselves. The use of instructional material is to simplify teaching and learning activities taking place in the classroom. Every

learning experience has its teaching aids that would promote learning and teaching. That is a function in more than one lesson. The fact remains that the whole body of knowledge is related to each other is simple and obvious that, teaching aids used for one lesson may be relevant and useful in the delivery of another lesson. But oftentimes, teachers do select the wrong teaching materials or aids for their teaching, and this made it impossible for the realization of the goals and objectives of teaching the lesson. Therefore, if this challenge must be overcome, teachers' teaching materials or teaching aids have to be supervised before use. This supervision will make for proper selection of teaching aids, and probably the teachers involved will also gain clarification on the utilization of such aids in the delivery of his/her lesson. This is an approach to promote teachers' job effectiveness in the use of teaching materials or aids (Mbang, 2002).

Ibok (2012) carried out a study on the supervision of teachers' teaching experience and effective job performance in selected secondary schools in Biase local government area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The researcher adopted the ex-post facto research design. A ten (10) item four-point rating scale questionnaire was used to obtain the data for the study. The designed instrument was validated and tested for reliability before it was administered to the respondents in the study area. The simple random sampling technique was used to select twelve (12) public secondary schools in the area, while the stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select five hundred and sixteen (516) teachers who are still in active service in the public secondary schools in the area. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study the independent t-test statistical analysis was used to establish the influence of effective supervision of teachers' teaching experience on effective job performance in the study area. The result from data analysis and testing of hypotheses showed that the calculated t-value of 0.867 is greater than the critical t-value of 0.195 when tested at the 0.05 level of significance with 514 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is a significant influence of supervision of teachers' teaching experience on effective job performance in selected secondary schools in Biase local government area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Based on the result of the finding it was recommended that school principals should engage in routine supervision of their teachers to enhance their wealth of experience in teaching.

The teaching profession is one profession that has more to do with the psychology of the people. The service of a professional counsellor is therefore required to maintain a balance in the teacher and learners' psychology. The learner's psychology is essential in promoting effective teaching and learning in the school setting. This is because the better the psychology of the learner, the easier the attainment and actualization of teaching goals and objectives, and vice versa. The teacher has to identify students who are psychologically traumatized, seek and obtain the service of a school counsellor for them and even ensure a follow-up to ensure that the student makes maximum use of the piece of advice given (Chris, 2002). Biodun (2010) conducted a study on effective school counselling services and teachers' job effectiveness in the public secondary schools in Lagos main towns. The survey research design was adopted to investigate the situation the way it happens presently. Twenty (20) private secondary schools were randomly selected and used for the study. The entire principal and vice-principals numbering forty (40) were purposively selected and used for the study. Five hundred (500) teachers were also randomly sampled and used for the study. The researcher designed, validated

and tested for reliability a fifteen (15) item questionnaire instrument on effective school counselling service and teachers' job effectiveness. Based on the result it was recommended that schools (private and public) should employ the service of qualified counsellors to provide such services to teachers when the need arises.

Etekepi and Akpan (2012) researched the availability of an effective school counsellor and teachers' job performance in selected secondary schools in Ikot Ekpene local government area of Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. Ten public secondary schools were selected randomly and used for the study. The sample for the study comprised 380 respondents. That is 180 male teachers and 200 female teachers respectively. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using descriptive simple Pearson product-moment correlation statistical analysis. The result from data analysis and testing of hypothesis in the study revealed that 300 respondents which are equivalent to (78.9%) agreed that, the availability of an effective school counsellor will promote teachers' job performance in the study area. On the other hand, 80(21.1%) represented respondents that accepted otherwise. Further, the result presented from the testing of the hypothesis showed that the calculated r-value of 0.966 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.195 when tested at the 0.05 level of significance with 378 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the availability of an effective school counsellor and teachers' job performance in selected secondary schools in Ikot Ekpene local government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on this finding it was recommended all schools should employ the service of a sound counsellor to help the students by giving them useful information and advice that would promote the attainment of school goals and teachers' job effectiveness.

Teachers are instrument par-excellence in promoting teaching/learning in the school system. It is very common to witness massive failure amongst students in both internal and external examinations in the study area. While parents/guardians, government, policymakers, and concerned individuals in the area blame students' poor performance on students and their family background. Though there might be no connection between students' poor performance and teachers' job effectiveness, it is evident that teachers in the area do not obtain the required assistance in the area of mentorship and capacity development. It may be necessary to address this very important area if teachers' job effectiveness is to be encouraged. The education system in Nigeria is challenged by several variables such as poor funding, ineffective teachers, poor infrastructure and policies. Teaching effectiveness is often seen as a significant predictor of students' academic achievement. This is because teaching effectiveness as a multi-dimensional construct measures a variety of different aspects of teaching such as subjects' mastery, effective communication, lesson preparation and presentation (Onyechu, 1996).

This issue of falling standards in education and students' academic performance has become a source of concern to all stakeholders in the academic industry. Most often, when these issues are raised and discussed, teachers are mostly blamed for the decline in the education sector. The contention has often been that teachers do not effectively perform their job resulting in low students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations. Despite these poor results, education stakeholders have continued to invest resources to reposition the

nation's educational system. The effort which is geared toward providing mentorship and capacity development has also enhanced effective supervision, guidance, modelling effective training in information and communication technology, a delegation of responsibility, in-service training and workshop attendance, to mention but a few. All these efforts are geared toward enhancing teachers' job effectiveness in the study area and beyond. However, this research work is conducted to investigate the extent to which mentorship, capacity development influences teachers' job effectiveness in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate mentorship, capacity development and teachers' job effectiveness in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Investigate the influence of supervision on teachers' job effectiveness
- ii. Investigate the influence of guidance on teachers' job effectiveness.

Research hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to direct this study;

- i. There is no significant influence of supervision on teachers' job effectiveness.
- ii. Guidance does not significantly influence teachers' job effectiveness?

Methods

The research area for this study is the Calabar Education Zone representing the Southern Senatorial District of Cross River State. The study area has a total population of 1,877, 554 people, (2006 census figures). It comprises seven local government areas namely; Akamkpa, Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Biase, Calabar Municipality, Calabar South and Odukpani Local Government Areas. The research design adopted for this study was the Ex- post facto research design. Kerlinger (1986) in Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim and Ekuri (2004) asserted that Ex-post facto research design is a systematic empirical inquiry in which the researcher does not have direct control of the independent variables because their manifestations have already occurred or because they are inherently not manipulable. Inferences about relations among variables are made without direct intervention from a concomitant variation of independent and dependent variables.

The targeted population of this study consists of all public secondary schools' teachers in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Statistics from the State Secondary Education Board reveal that there are two thousand two hundred and eighty-two (2,382) teachers in the seventy-two (72) Public Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone. The purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting all the public secondary schools in the seven Local Government Areas that make up the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The purposive sampling technique was adopted based on the fact that teachers who make up

the sample of the study possess the characteristics needed by the researcher. In selecting the sample to be used for the study, the simple random sampling technique was adopted. The researcher adopted the technique to give equal opportunity to all the respondents to be selected for the study. All those willing to participate were to take part in a simple balloting exercise. The researcher through this technique selected 20% of respondents used for the study. According to Boll and Gall (1971), for a population of up to 1000 the researcher should use 21% of the population as the sample size. Therefore, the study sample consisted of five hundred respondents (500) respondents from the public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

The instrument for data collection in the study is a questionnaire. It was tagged "Mentorship, Capacity Development and Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (MCDTJEQ)". To ensure that the items selected for inclusion in the questionnaire are capable of eliciting relevant responses from respondents, the researcher sent a constructed questionnaire to three assessors – one in test and measurement, the others in educational management. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the validated copy of the instrument was trial tested. A Cronbach reliability coefficient of .83 was obtained for the instrument. Data obtained from respondents were tested using independent t-test analysis. The analysis was aided by SPSS (version 21).

Results

Hypothesis 1

The null form of this hypothesis stated that supervision does not significantly influence teachers' job effectiveness. In testing this hypothesis, the independent t-test analysis was carried out at the .05 level of significance. To permit the use of this statistical, procedure, supervision was categorized into 'high' and 'low' based on the respondents' scores on the variable in the instrument. Respondents with scores ranging from the mean to the maximum score (33-36) were categorized 'high', while those who scored below the mean (26-32) were categorized 'low'. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Independent t-test analysis of the influence of supervision on teachers' job effectiveness

Teachers' job effectiveness	Level of supervision	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Maintenance of discipline	High	291	18.84	0.88	1.187	.236
	Low	209				
Classroom control	High	291	21.98	1.35	.997	.319
	Low	209	21.86	1.15		
Lesson presentation	High	291	19.01	0.86	.269	.788
	Low	209	18.97			
Students' assessment	High	291	18.89	0.84	1.290	.198
	Low	209	18.98	0.69		

df = 498

As shown in Table 1, the p-values associated with the teachers' job effectiveness variables were each greater than the chosen level of significance for the study (.05). Based on this outcome, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternative. This means that the supervision of teachers does not significantly influence their job effectiveness in terms of maintenance of discipline, classroom control, and lesson presentation and students' assessment. This result is in agreement with the findings of Udowong (2014) which similarly that showed that the supervision of teaching aids promote teachers' role effectiveness in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State; From the foregone, it shows that supervision of teaching aids is essential in promoting teachers' role effectiveness in the study area. Based on the results obtained from the findings, it was recommended that adequate supervisory strategies should be put in place to promote effective monitoring and supervision of teachers' role effectiveness in the study area.

Hypothesis 2

This hypothesis stated that guidance does not significantly influence teachers' job effectiveness. The independent t-test analysis was applied in testing these hypotheses at the .05 level of significance. Guidance was categorized as 'high' and 'low' to permit the use of this statistical procedure. Respondents scores on the variable from the mean to the maximum score (26-28) were categorized 'high' those below the mean (21-25) were categorized 'low'. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent t-test analysis of the influence of guidance on teachers' job effectiveness

Teachers' job effectiveness	Level of guidance	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Maintenance of discipline	High	360	18.74	0.81	2.062	.040
	Low	140	18.92	1.13		
Classroom control	High	360	21.94	1.30	.464	.643
	Low	140	21.88	1.19		
Lesson presentation	High	360	19.11	1.94	2.327	.020
	Low	140	18.91	1.01		
Students' assessment	High	360	18.82	0.81	5.134	.000
	Low	140	19.21	0.62		

df = 498

From Table 2, the p-values against the maintenance of discipline (.040) lesson presentation (.020) and students' discipline (.040) lesson presentation (.020) and students' assessment (.000) were each less than the chosen level of significance (.05). The p-value (.643) against classroom control as however, greater than .05. Based on these outcomes the null hypothesis was rejected for all job effectiveness variables, except classroom control. It was therefore concluded that the guidance of teachers significantly influenced teachers' job effectiveness except for classroom control. The result of this finding is in line with the findings of Biodun (2010) a significant effective school counselling service on teachers' job effectiveness. Based on the result it was recommended that schools (private and public) should

employ the service of qualified counsellors to provide such services to teachers when the need arises.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of the hypotheses in the study, it can be concluded that the supervision of teachers significantly influences their job effectiveness in terms of maintenance of discipline, classroom control, lesson presentation and students' assessment. The guidance of teachers significantly influences their teachers' job effectiveness except for classroom control.

Recommendations

From the findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypotheses in the study, the researcher would make the following recommendations;

1. Relevant authorities should ensure that secondary school teachers are adequately and regularly motivated to take part in capacity development programmes to enable them to perform maximally as required.
2. There should be a motivation package provided for all teachers to enable them to engage in further studies to upgrade and deliver as expected of them in the teaching profession.
3. Teachers should be supervised and monitored adequately to keep them active and equip with the 21st classroom teaching and learning experiences, as well as encourage those with quality performance while correcting those who tend to live below expectations.

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